

in treated seeds, showing that the fungus was internally borne, or at least present inside the seed coat.

Seedlings produced from the seed samples confirmed the presence of fungus in the vascular system. Bakanae symptoms appeared on plants grown to maturity.

Reisolation of the pathogen and back-inoculation to other rice plants confirmed its pathogenicity. □

Effect of grain discoloration in upland rice on some yield components

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The main causal agents of grain discoloration (GD) in upland rice in West Sumatra are different species of fungi, with *Helminthosporium oryzae* being the most important. Symptoms vary from spots invisible to the naked eye to a completely rotten endosperm. In susceptible varieties, the disease can cause complete yield loss.

We collected 50 panicles of susceptible upland rice variety Tondano in the Sitiung area and separated them into five groups, with disease severities of 1, 10, 30, 60, and 100%. Seeds of each severity

Rice seeds from different localities showing percent bakanae disease infection in Pakistan.

Locality	Seeds ^a showing <i>F. moniliforme</i> (%)		Seedlings showing <i>F. moniliforme</i> in vascular system (%)	Bakanae disease symptoms (%) in plants grown from untreated seeds
	Treated ^b	Untreated		
Amin Abad	9.5	6.2	10	6
Daska	6.0	1.5	6	7
G. G. Khan	0.0	0.0	0	0
Gujranwala	19.8	9.5	17	8
Hafiz Abad	11.0	7.2	12	7
Kala Shah Kaku	12.2	5.5	10	9
Narang Mandi	8.8	1.8	9	11
Sheikhupura	11.5	7.2	13	11
Sialkot	12.2	11.8	10	9

^aMean of 4 counts. ^bWith 0.1% mercuric chloride for 1 min.

group were planted in plastic trays (33 seeds/tray per replication) and grown in the greenhouse, to determine the effect of the disease on germination and plant height. Additional panicles of each severity group (3 panicles/replication) were used to study the effect of disease on grains/panicle. Weight of 100 grains was calculated for each severity group,

with three replications.

The higher the disease severity, the lower the germination and seedling height (see table). The disease reduced germination as much as 40% and reduced seedling height 3-20%. The higher the severity, the more the empty grains/panicle, with parallel weight reduction. □

Effect of rice grain discoloration on some yield components.^a

Severity of grain discoloration (%)	Germination ^b (%)	Seedling height ^c (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)				Weight of 100 grains ^e (g)	Reduction in weight (%10)
			Filled ^d	%	Empty	%		
1	92 a	10.9 (91) a	140 a	94	9 b	6	3.09 a	-
10	81 a	10.6 (86) a	137 a	90	16 b	10	2.94 a	5
30	80 bc	10.2 (79) a	135 a	91	14 b	9	2.95 a	4
60	73 c	9.7 (72) ab	101 b	74	35 a	26	2.56 b	17
100	52 d	8.7 (52) b	118 b	78	33 a	22	2.27 c	26

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not statistically different at a probability level of 0.05. ^bAv from 3 replications, 33 seeds/replication. ^cAv from 3 replications. Values in parentheses are total number of seedlings. ^dAv from 3 replications, 3 panicles/replication. ^eAv from 3 replications, 100 seeds/replication.

Integrated pest management—insects

Duration of diapause in white stem borer (SB) *Scirpophaga innotata*

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The white SB replaced the yellow SB *S. incertulas* in many parts of the northern coast of West Java in the 1989-90 wet season.

Replacement of improved Cisadane, a

135-d variety, with IR64 (110 d) lengthened the fallow period between dry and wet season crops to 3 mo. That favored the white SB, which can aestivate as prepupae at the base of rice stubble. The outbreak destroyed 15,000 ha of rice in the command area of the Jatiluhur Irrigation System (JIS) in Karawang, Subang, and Indramayu districts.

The JIS is divided into five regions of staggered water delivery. At Sukamandi, rice is transplanted ahead of that in Karawang. We collected aestivating prepupae from Karawang (52 d after

harvest) and Sukamandi (96 d after harvest) and subjected them to artificial rainfall and to flooding, to simulate land preparation for rice.

Frequency and amount of rainfall was based on the previous year's pattern. Water was poured onto prepupae in rice stubble placed in pots. Excised prepupae were placed individually in 12-cm-long, 0.5-cm-dim plastic drinking straws with cotton plugs in both ends. The straws were placed with the bottom cotton plug in contact with standing water, to simulate flooding.

Both watering methods terminated aestivation. The prepupae in the untreated